

The Effect of Electronic Service Quality on Customer Loyalty Through Customer Satisfaction

(Survey of Customer at AirAsia Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, Jakarta in 2021)

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Abstract:- In the world of aviation, airlines are required to always keep abreast of advances in technology and information. Because the development of technology and information have influenced people's lifestyles in carrying out activities from conventional to online shopping. Airlines also need to evaluate e-service quality to build customer loyalty in long-term relationships. The research method uses a quantitative method approach.

Keywords:- *Electronic Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Entering the globalization period, industrial revolution 4.0 and society 5.0, which makes humans more contemporary since they have access to technology and these technologies are ingrained in them. Airlines battle fiercely to stay afloat by releasing the latest technological breakthroughs. This is also done to catch clients' attention so that they can use the airline's services.

AirAsia Airlines has implemented an online check-in system to keep up with the advancement of technology. The online check-in process is available on the official AirAsia website, airasia.com, as well as the AirAsia app, which can be downloaded from the App Store and Play Store. AirAsia indirectly leads customers to be up-to-date on technology changes by implementing this online check-in system, which also saves queuing time at the check-in counter when many flight schedules are available at the same time.

Online check-in and the usage of self-check-in machines are examples of using electronic service quality or technology as a foundation for carrying out other online operations carried out by the airline. To reduce the likelihood of late check-in, the airline offers an online check-in option that can be completed up to two hours prior to departure. The terms and regulations of online check-in differ depending on the airline. Online check-in is available on each airline's website or via the app.

Because the transportation industry is a service industry founded on the notion of trust, customer trust is a critical aspect in determining the company's success. In an era of ever-increasing competition, every business must strive to not just survive, but also to compete and grow. Retaining existing clients is one of the most critical things that businesses must do in order to survive and thrive. Customers will be loyal, according to Kotler and Keller (2013), provided their requirements are addressed and they are happy.

Even in an airline broadening services by providing numerous sorts and advantages, airlines are increasingly issuing new service innovations that are superior. Customers who require and demand quality services, prices, and benefits supplied at competitive price levels are a possible influencer on customer loyalty that manufacturers must pay attention to.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This study tries to answer the following questions:

- Does electronic service quality have an impact on AirAsia customer loyalty?
- Does electronic service quality have an impact on AirAsia customer satisfaction?
- Does customer satisfaction have a relationship on AirAsia customer loyalty?
- Does electronic service quality have an impact on customer loyalty as mediated by AirAsia customer satisfaction?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Electronic Service Quality*

Electronic service quality, according to Fauzi (2018), is defined as overall client assessments and judgments of the excellence and quality of electronic service delivery in the virtual marketplace.

Customers view service quality differently on a website or in an online environment than they do with traditional services (Amin 2016). Server issues, data backup, connectivity issues, and other issues that are particular to online services

are not encountered by offline services (Collier & Bienstock, 2016).

The use of high-quality electronic services should result in increased efficiency and effectiveness in operational tasks. Benefits include: making the task easier, being more valuable, and increasing productivity. As well as efficiency, which includes increasing efficiency and improving job performance.

According to the above description, the quality of electronic services is a service provided by utilizing technological advances in order for operational activities to run effectively and efficiently, as well as encouraging customers to stay current with technological developments in order to shift their lifestyles from traditional to online.

➤ *Customer Satisfaction*

The words "satisfaction" and "factio" are Latin words that imply "good enough, adequate" (meaning to do or make). Satisfaction is described as "efforts to fulfill something" or "to make something adequate" in basic terms. Tjptono (2011).

Customer satisfaction, according to Normasari (2013), is the level of one's feelings after analyzing the service performance they anticipate against their expectations.

Customer satisfaction, according to Kotler (2014: 150), is defined as "feelings of joy or disappointment that come after comparing the performance (results) of the product to the expected performance" (or results).

According to Handriati et al., (2015), customer satisfaction is defined as the result (outcome) of a customer's feelings about using a product or service that meets or surpasses their expectations. As a result, client happiness is extremely vital and critical to a company's existence and growth.

Customer satisfaction, according to Bahrudin & Zuhro (2016), is a very valuable design in marketing design and customer research because it is a general response that if customers are satisfied with something offered, they are more likely to reuse it and tell others about their positive experience with the goods or services provided.

According to the above definition, the synthesis of customer satisfaction is the result of a service provided by service providers to service users, whether or not it meets their expectations, so that if the customer is satisfied with the product or service provided, the customer will remain loyal and repurchase the product or service. providing input/suggestions to the company, suggesting products/services to others, willing to pay extra, and providing input/suggestions to the firm.

➤ *Customer Loyalty*

"Loyalty is defined as non random purchasing manifested over time by some decision making unit," according to Griffin in Sangadji and Sopiah (2013:104). According to this definition, loyalty refers to the decision-making unit's behavioral form of making continuous purchases of goods or services from a specific organization.

According to Suwondo & Marjan (2017), customer loyalty is defined as a consumer's good perception of the company, responsibility for repurchasing the company's products or services, and ability to suggest the product or service to others. Customer loyalty, according to Siagian & Cahyono (2014), is one of the most important outcomes of an online business. Meanwhile, Normasari (2013) claims that client loyalty is a valuable commodity with a big role in the industry.

The synthesis of customer loyalty is defined as a customer's attitude or behavior in committing to service users in deciding whether or not to reuse the service, which is obtained by having a sense of trust in service providers because the services provided meet their expectations, with the result that customers are willing to recommend products/services that are offered. presented to others in the hopes that others may be interested in moving and following their advice.

➤ *Research Method*

This study employs a quantitative approach. The quantitative approach is a kind of study that generates numerical data, which is then examined using descriptive or inferential statistics (Silaen, 2018). The numbers acquired are analyzed to see how they affect the formulation of the research problem that has been determined. Is the proposed hypothesis supported by the survey results? Do the figures suggest that we're correct about the issue at hand? Etc.

The passengers of AirAsia were the study's target population. In a year, the author estimates that 2.148.968 passengers pass through Soekarno-Hatta International Airport. 210 passengers were chosen as research samples from the overall population.

IV. RESULT

➤ *Validity Test*

The critical limit of validity has a value of 0.361. The questionnaire item is invalid if the correlation value or r count is less than or equal to 0.361. The items on the questionnaire, on the other hand, are certified valid if the estimated r-value is larger than 0.361. Table 1 shows how to test the validity of the research instrument (questionnaire) for each of the variables evaluated.

Table 1. Validity Test Result

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Result
Electronic Service Quality	X1	0.907	Valid
	X2	0.944	Valid
	X3	0.895	Valid
	X4	0.947	Valid
	X5	0.903	Valid
	X6	0.947	Valid
	X7	0.931	Valid
	X8	0.940	Valid
	X9	0.916	Valid
	X10	0.907	Valid
	X11	0.910	Valid
	X12	0.910	Valid
	X13	0.910	Valid
	X14	0.910	Valid
Customer Satisfaction	Y1	0.907	Valid
	Y2	0.976	Valid
	Y3	0.965	Valid
	Y4	0.805	Valid
Customer Loyalty	Z1	0.881	Valid
	Z2	0.868	Valid
	Z3	0.826	Valid

Source: Primary data, processed by SmartPLS.

The value of the outer model, or the correlation between the construct and the variable, reveals that the total value of the loading factor is greater than 0.5, indicating that the constructions for all variables are valid from the model, as shown in table 1. The outer model's structural model yielded the following result.

Picture 1. Outer Structural Model

➤ Discriminant Validity Test

Table 2. Discriminant Validity Test Result

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Electronic Service Quality (X)	0.846
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.839
Customer Loyalty (Z)	0.737

Source: Primary data, processed by SmartPLS.

This test was carried out to determine how much each variable differed. This test displays the average variance extracted (AVE) value for each variable. If the value is more than 0.50, they are considered valid.

➤ Reliability Test

Table 3. Reliability Test Result

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Rule of Thumb	Evaluasi Model
Electronic Service Quality (X)	0.986	0.987	> 0.70	Reliable
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.934	0.954		Reliable
Customer Loyalty (Z)	0.825	0.894		Reliable

Source: Primary data, processed by SmartPLS.

Because the Cronbach Alpha coefficient is 0.70, or better than 0.70, Table 3 shows that the overall alpha value is dependable (reliable). The statement items created from each variable can be used and delivered to all 210 passengers who have been targeted as respondents, based on the findings of the validity and reliability analysis indicated above. As a result, it is clear that the items produce valid and dependable findings. Further analysis can be done based on these findings.

➤ Inner Model Test

The relationship between the construct, significant value, and R-square of the research model is tested using the inner model or structural model. For the dependent construct of the t-test and the significance of the coefficients of the structural route parameters, the structural model was evaluated using R-square.

Picture 2. Inner Structural Model

When using PLS to evaluate a model, the first step is to look at the R-square and Q-square for each dependent latent variable. Table 4 shows the R-square and Q-square estimation results using SmartPLS.

Table 4. R Square Value

Variable	R Square
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0,525
Customer Loyalty (Z)	0,393

In theory, this study employs two variables that are influenced by other factors. The R Square value of the Customer Satisfaction variable (Y) is 0.525, or 52.5 percent, indicating that the Electronic Service Quality variable (X) can significantly explain the Customer Satisfaction variable (Y) with a level of 52.5 percent, while the rest is influenced by other factors not included. into this research's variables The R Square value of the Customer Loyalty variable (Z) is 0.393, or 39.3 percent, indicating that the Electronic Service Quality (X) and Customer Satisfaction (Y) variables can substantially explain the Customer Loyalty variable (Z) with a level of 39.3 percent, while the remainder is influenced by other factors not included in the variables of this study.

➤ Hypothesis Testing

The significance of the estimated parameters gives us a lot of information about how the research variables are related. The value provided in the output path coefficient is the basis for testing the hypothesis.

➤ Direct Effect Analysis

Table 5. Direct Effect Analysis

Variable	X → Z	X → Y	Y → Z
Original Sample (O)	0.724	0.166	0.496
Sample Mean (M)	0.726	0.171	0.500
Standard Deviation (STDEV)	0.034	0.075	0.082
T Statistics (O/STDEV)	21.124	2.220	6.038
P Values	0.000	0.027	0.000
Keterangan	H1 accepted	H2 accepted	H3 accepted

Source: primary data, processed by SmartPLS.

Hypothesis testing can be explained as follows based on the above:

- Testing the hypothesis of the Effect of Electronic Service Quality on Service Loyalty yields a t statistic of 21.124, which is greater than 1.97, and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, implying that there is a positive and significant relationship between Service Quality Electronics and Customer Loyalty.
- Testing hypotheses The effect of Electronic Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction has a t-statistics value of 2.220, which is higher than 1.97, and a p-value of 0.027, which is lower than 0.05, indicating that there is a positive and significant relationship between Service Quality Electronics and Customer Satisfaction.
- Testing the hypothesis of the effect of customer satisfaction on service loyalty yields a t statistic of 6.038, which is greater than 1.97, and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, implying that there is a positive and significant relationship between Service Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction.

➤ Indirect Effect Analysis

Table 6. Indirect Effect Analysis

Variable	X → Z through Y
Original Sample (O)	0.359
Sample Mean (M)	0.363
Standard Deviation	0.061
T Statistics	5.853
P Values	0.000
Result	H4 accepted

Source: primary data, processed by SmartPLS.

Based on the hypothesis testing of the effect of Electronic Service Quality on Customer Loyalty through Service Satisfaction, the t statistics value of 5.853 is greater than 1.97 and the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, indicating that Electronic Service Quality has a positive and significant impact on Customer Loyalty through Service Satisfaction.

V. DISCUSSION

- **H1**, relationship between electronic service quality and customer loyalty has p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$ and t stat $21.214 > 1.97$, implying that electronic service quality has a positive and significant impact on customer loyalty. Customer loyalty is influenced by the electronic service quality.
- **H2**, with p-values of $0.027 < 0.05$ and a t-stat of $2.220 > 1.97$ for electronic service quality to customer satisfaction, it can be inferred that the electronic service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Customer happiness is influenced by the electronic service quality.
- **H3**, With p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$ and t stat $6.038 > 1.97$, it can be stated that customer satisfaction has a positive and substantial effect on customer loyalty.
- **H4**, With p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$ and t stat $5.853 > 1.72$ for electronic service quality to customer loyalty through customer satisfaction mediation, it can be inferred that electronic service quality has a positive and substantial effect on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction mediation.

VI. CONCLUSION

Some conclusions can be taken from the research findings and overall analysis as follows:

- The electronic service quality has a significant and positive direct effect on AirAsia customer loyalty in 2021.
- The electronic service quality has a significant and positive direct effect on AirAsia customer satisfaction in 2021.
- Customer satisfaction has a significant and positive direct effect on AirAsia customer loyalty in 2021.
- The electronic service quality has a significant indirect effect on AirAsia customer loyalty in 2021 which is mediated by customer satisfaction.

VII. RECOMMENDATION

The authors make the following suggestions and recommendations based on the foregoing conclusions:

- AirAsia can ensure that the order refund status on the website/app is always up to date, allowing the refund procedure to be completed within the stipulated time frame.
- AirAsia can ensure that all customer concerns are adequately addressed, ensuring that customers are not disappointed.
- AirAsia can improve online check-in so that there are no lines at the check-in counter when there are numerous nearby flight itineraries.
- In order for customer to make the best use of the facilities, AirAsia must provide simple explanations.
- AirAsia can verify that customers have no difficulty accessing the website/application. Customers will not have any problems accessing the website/application as a result of this.
- Additional researchers conducting research on the quality of electronic services are recommended to look at other characteristics that have a substantial impact in addition to

client loyalty and satisfaction. As a result, it is envisaged that these studies would be valuable in offering feedback and recommendations to businesses and academic institutions.

VIII. IMPLICATION

The following are the implications based on the research findings and the above-mentioned recommendations:

- If a refund is required, AirAsia can handle it differently so that customers can reclaim their rights.
- AirAsia can create new means to communicate with consumers so that each customer's requirements or complaints get the greatest possible attention.
- Create a Q&A section with answers to frequently asked questions so that clients may quickly access the website/application.
- Creating a simple self-check-in machine that encourages clients to perform their own check-in rather than going via the check-in counter.
- Make sure the website/application runs well, and schedule server maintenance for times when visitors aren't around.

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